

Ecological Awareness of High School Students in Coimbatore District

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ABSTRACT

In this study, high school students awareness of ecological issues and problems and the level of their active participation in ecological activities have been identified, and the effects of some factors as family school and media on their ecological awareness and active participation have been investigated. The study was carried out in Coimbatore schools by conducting a survey on senior students consisting of 6 classes from three high schools which have different demographic and socio-economic levels. The results of the study showed a high level of ecological awareness among participant students. However, it is understood that ecological disclosures made in schools are insufficient and the participation level of students to ecological activities is low. Students rather gain experiences in the field of environment from mass media (i.e. audio, printed and visual media). It is revealed that female students have a higher level of ecological awareness and active participation level. In addition, when family income and family education level increases, ecological awareness and active participation level of students also increases.

INTRODUCTION

At the dawn of the 21st century, a powerful and complex web of interactions has contributed to unprecedented global trends in ecology degradation. These include rapid globalization, urbanization, poverty, unsustainable consumption patterns and population growth. They have served to compound the effects and intensity of the global ecology problems. Global climate change, depletion of the ozone layer, desertification, deforestation, loss of the planets biological diversity, trans-boundary movements of hazardous wastes and chemicals are all ecology problems that touch every nation and adversely affect the lives and health of their populations.

The level of global ecology challenges is now beyond serious scientific dispute. In cognizance of the role of an informed and educated citizenry in making appropriate ecology decisions and adopting behavioral approach in addressing ecology challenges, the concept of ecological Education (EE) was born. The importance of eco- logical Education (EE) is recognized and emphasized as one of the most effective ways, if not the only way, to meet the complicated problems of the environment. The call for EE is therefore a call for local, regional and global action in response to the biophysical and social problems of the abused environments of the whole world. It is a call to educational system that fosters or encourages the development of ecology literate citizens who share concern for the environment in which they live and in which future generations will also have to live. EE finds its formal root in the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm of 1972. This conference recommended establishment of an International ecological Education Programme.. It recommended the primary categories of ecology education curriculum goals and objectives comprising of ecology awareness, attitudes, skills and participation, which comprise the subject of this study. The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 reiterated, in Agenda 21, that through EE, school children are obliged to participate actively in guarding the quality of the environment. This is because they comprise half of the world population and are highly vulnerable to the effects of ecology degradation now and in the future. Moreover, secondary school students are usually receptive and strongly motivated and are capable of understanding the implications of ecology destruction and of trying to take preventive action. However, for school

children to meaningfully participate in ecology conservation activities, they require knowledge and skills gained through EE. These qualities are personal thought, feeling and action which develop in the students through an educational process that creates awareness, develops attitude and builds capacity and willingness to take action as an individual and as a group.

The contradiction between explosion and fragmentation of demand on one hand, and the unemployment which affects an ever growing number of graduates on the other, between the provision of equal access and opportunity and the financial constraints upon the mass extension of higher education; and finally between ethical and moral obligations and the various incitements of knowledge and discoveries. Faced with such tensions and paradoxes, higher education must develop a new vision, take advantage of its adaptability, flexibility and imaginative resources in order to develop problem-solving and forward looking capacities equip itself with an ever watchful critical spirit and promote team work, without ever jettisoning its role as ethical watch-dog. The issue of quality cannot be dissociated from the quest of excellence and the need to establish evaluation criteria. Many countries are calling for international quality standards. Such criteria and standards should take account of the diversity of situations. The need to develop a culture of evaluation is inseparable from the concept of quality itself intimately bound up with the successful democratization of the higher education system. Following the evolution of green ecology practices, most communities put their strategies in motion in order to minimize the ecology impacts and reach a sustainability to hold positive attributes of environment.. The causes of these negative effects are manifested by colonization with the ongoing destruction of environment for paving new lands. Climate change as in global warming we are facing, External forces affecting the earth atmosphere by changing compositions and increasing greenhouse effects. Species extinction, reduction of biodiversity, various forms of pollution and pollutants, desertification, deforestation, poverty, lands erosion, disease and hunger, migration and radioactive related disasters, population growth, to name a few. First step in order to combat such degradation was to form the social movements which then crystallized into ecologyism and green movements. These societies based on Green politics, an ideology with goals of

maintaining sustainable ecological ecologyism which is already spread across the globe with some success in some extents. The concept of sustainable development recently has been added to the movement which complements and guides the whole process and discourse. The severity of the issue/problem has resulted in establishment of formal ecology institutions within the governmental structures, as well as grassroots movements through formation of N.G.O.s around the world. These movements are diverse in scientific, social and political with the management of resources and changes in public policies with individual behaviors of humanity in mind to protect ecology and biosphere in general. Nowadays we have ecology law organizations across the world which follows regulations on monitory system that consists of property rights, citizens rights and natures rights. The concerns of ecologists and related movements transcend dominant anthropocentric philosophy and try to replace it with eco-centric behavior. The interaction between people and the environment is complex, and influenced by a variety of factors such as cultural and scientifically. Humans do not just exist solely in environment, they constantly changing and transforming it. Many science fields are already put into motion for assessing and incorporating human relationships.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Altunta, E. ., & Turan, S. L. (2018) studied aims to identify secondary school students level of awareness of renewable energy sources. The study's method combined quantitative and qualitative research techniques. A five-point Likert scale was developed to quantitatively measure awareness of these energy sources. The scale was analysed for validity and reliability, and it addressed cognitive and affective sub-dimensions of awareness. A semi structured. interview form was developed for the qualitative part of the study. Two sample groups were chosen for the study. The sample group for the quantitative part comprised 300 secondary school students; for the qualitative part, 5to interviews. The results revealed that the students awareness of renewable energy sources was at an intermediate level and there was a significant correlation between their cognitive and affective awareness. Furthermore, there were significant differences in the participants grade level, field of study, source of information, and awareness of renewable energy sources.

Mainaki, R., Kastolani, W., & Setiawan, I. (2018) explained ecology degradation caused by the high volume of vehicles, industrial activity, population growth and conversion of green open space. It is therefore necessary for human-based efforts to reduce the degradation of the environment. One of them can be done through the growth of ecological intelligence. The most effective growth of ecological intelligence at the age of 12 to 18 years. It is an age where humans are in secondary school. The growth of ecological intelligence can be done through school culture with ecology content in it. This research uses survey method based on quantitative approach and correlational research design. The technique of determining the number of samples using stratified random sampling, obtained 36 schools and 260 students. Data were collected by observation techniques, interviews, questionnaires, literature studies and documentation studies. The results showed that school culture has correlation with ecology condition. Thus, the exemplary aspect of teachers, principals, and educators has efforts to preserve the environment on school culture. The habitualization of school residents in preserving the environment in the school culture should be a centralized standard rule. Hansen, W. D., Scholl, J. P., Sorensen, A. E., Fisher, K. E., Klassen, J. A., Calle, L., & Narango, D. L. (2018). described Ecology must attract and retain diverse talented people to produce innovative research and relevant solutions to 21st century ecology problems. Careers and culture form the foundation of scientific advancement, and substantial progress has been made over recent decades in both realms. Yet, important challenges persist in expanding career paths, inclusion of underrepresented groups, and communication with the public. The ESA Student Section organized a horizon scanning exercise to address the following goals: (1) to identify challenges that 21st century ecologists contend with or expect to contend with in careers and outreach to society, (2) to anticipate opportunities to help ecologists meet challenges, and (3) to identify concrete steps that could be taken by individual laboratories, institutions, and the ESA to foster progress. In spring 2016, the ESA Student Section solicited input from student members and organized a working group to assess the state of the discipline and to envision how we might cultivate a more inclusive and effective community. We identified three major challenges. First, PhDs are produced faster than academic positions become available and disconnects between academia and other sectors may keep early

career ecologists from realizing the breadth of available positions. We propose an online jobs hub to make nonacademic sectors more accessible to ecologists. We also suggest students develop skills portfolios to prepare for nonacademic positions. Second, the composition of people who are ecologists differs from broader society, partially due to implicit biases and institutional barriers. We propose steps to reduce attrition of diversity in ecology that include countering implicit biases and creating mentorship networks. We offer steps to improve recruitment by increasing awareness of ecology among high school students and undergraduates and providing opportunities to engage in ecological research. Finally, ecology is only relevant if the public perceives it to be. We must improve science communication and begin cultivating trust. We propose that ad hoc communication by all ecologists is insufficient; translational ecologists should be hired in every department and formal training in translational ecology is necessary.

Chen, Z., Zhang, Y., Bai, Q., Chen, B., Zhu, Y., & Xiong, Y. (2017) developed With the evolution of the mobile platform and the rapid adoption of mobile devices such as cell phones and other handheld devices, mobile devices are playing a huge role in education. The traditional teaching mode cannot meet the requirements of comprehensive quality cultivation for students in the information technology environment. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of different teaching model (PBL teaching model based on the mobile devices vs. traditional teaching model) on the meta-cognitive awareness of learners. One hundred and three primary school students enrolled in the Movement of the Earth course taught by the experienced professor. This study randomly selected one class as the experimental group and the other as the control group. The teacher used PBL teaching model based on the mobile devices in the experimental group and used traditional teaching mode in the control group. Quantitative analysis combined with qualitative analysis was used to examine the meta-cognitive awareness, learning achievement and students work. The results showed that PBL teaching based on mobile devices has better effect on students meta-cognitive awareness but there no significant difference with control group; Compared with the traditional teaching, PBL teaching based on mobile devices has a significant positive impact on students learning achievement; During the whole teaching process, students in the experimental

group played an active part in inquiry activities and did rich works. Song, Y. L., & Chung, H. (2017) studied study lies in examining what kind of topics regarding food ethics are being covered in South Korean middle school technology/home economics textbooks in an effort to help improve adolescents awareness of food ethics. To achieve the goals of the present study, the characteristics of food ethics in the nations middle school technology/home economics textbooks were analyzed based on the system of the contents of food ethics presented by Byun (2015). Based on our analysis on what kind of topics were covered in the textbooks for each course, the existing curriculum for middle school technology/home economics course one covered nutrition and health, and course two covered dietary life environment, production and consumption of environment-friendly food. Our analysis regarding the contents for each topic revealed that the production centered contents mainly addressed food-safety and circulation; distribution-centered contents focused mainly on food mileage and a small portion on ecology pollution; and consumption-centered contents addressed ethical consumption and sustainable meals. With the results of this study, the curriculum related to food ethics can be further developed leading to help the nations youth realize that food is not limited solely to health and enjoyment, but also entails both rights and responsibilities within the contents that were covered. Andersson, F. O., & Ford, M. R. (2016) developed new ideas and new organizations to address social challenges are central features in current social entrepreneurship research, and over the past two decades scholars have proposed a variety of approaches to understand and analyze these and other dimensions of social entrepreneurship. This article looks at social entrepreneurship from an ecological perspective and proposes that organizational ecology has much to offer this emerging field. Specifically, the article draws from a unique dataset on voucher schools in Milwaukee, Wisconsin to analyze the emergence as well as dynamics of this nonprofit population. Olufemi, A. C., Mji, A., & Mukhola, M. S. (2016) compared the levels of awareness, knowledge and attitudes (AKA) about ecology pollution of secondary school students from two South African provinces. The purpose was to determine the levels of AKA between students living under different ecology conditions. These two groups were students from a coal-mining province (Mpumalanga) and those from a non-coal-mining province (Gauteng). Participants were 753 purposively selected students from Grades 8

to 12 from the two the provinces thus: 423 from Mpumalanga province and 330 from Gauteng province. Their ages ranged from 13 to 23 years ($M = 16.1$; $SD = 1.75$). They responded to a 36-item awareness, knowledge and attitude questionnaire ($r = 0.77$) on issues relating to ecology pollution. Data were analysed through computing descriptive statistics followed by unpaired t-tests. Statistically significant differences were established between students from the two provinces with regards to all the ecology variables tested, where students from Mpumalanga province had higher mean scores than their counterparts from Gauteng. Students from both provinces identified newspapers as the most important source of information on ecology pollution.

il, E. (2015) explored Students need to be aware of plants in order to learn about, appreciate, care for and protect them. However, research has found that many children are not aware of the plants in their environment. A way to address this issue might be integration of plants with various disciplines. I investigated the effectiveness of an instructional approach based on integration of botany with chemistry and art for increasing students awareness of plants. The study was carried out in a science summer school for 10- to 12-year-old students ($n = 25$). A plant awareness questionnaire and a plant blindness test were used as pretests and posttests to assess the effects of the instruction on the students plant awareness. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with the students after instruction. The results indicated that integrating plants with various disciplines might overcome the learning problem of students associated with their plant blindness. Moreover, this instructional approach can provide students opportunities to learn the names of plants and some concepts in the botanical discipline, as well as help them understand the relationship between plants and other disciplines.

Aminrad, Z., Zakariya, S. Z. B. S., Hadi, A. S., & Sakari, M. (2013). discussed importance of ecology education (EE) is well known globally among societies. ecological education is gradually promoted as a sustainable tool in protection of the environment ecological education is found across school curriculums in Malaysia. The objectives of the curriculum are ecology attitude, knowledge and awareness (AKA) where has been investigated in the current study. The study was conducted to identify the relationship between ecology awareness,

knowledge and attitude among secondary school students. The survey was conducted on 470 respondents who were in Form Four (16 years old) in Kajang city, Selangor, Malaysia. An instrument which included (48 questions) was employed to investigate the relationship between awareness, knowledge and attitude. The results of Person Correlation showed a significant but weak relationship between awareness and knowledge on ecology issues while there was high relationship observed between awareness and attitudes among respondents. Moreover, the statistical test showed a negligible relationship between knowledge and attitude among students about environment. The study concluded that a high level of awareness and knowledge plus positive attitude of students may come have been achieved from the families of respondents, teachers, media, private reading and school curriculums regarding the environment that increases the ecology view among students as well as overall in the society. The study recommended that ecology education subject necessarily might be considered as an independent syllabus in Malaysian education system. Hong, J. S., Cho, H., Allen-Meares, P., & Espelage, D. L. (2011). studied Columbine High School shooting in 1999 prompted school officials and policy-makers to create and implement programs and policies that would prevent violence in school and ensure school safety. Ten years have passed since the Columbine shooting; however, debates concerning risk factors for the shootings continue to ensue. The focus of this article is to examine the Columbine school shootings within the context of Bronfenbrenners (1994) ecological systems analysis. We examine the most commonly identified risk factors, which operate within five systems levels: chrono-, macro-, exo-, meso-, and microsystems, and draw implications for school-based practice and policy. Geetha, T., & Maheshwari, K. (2018) figured by Lacan can be identified with the father figures in *The Rainbow*. The readers do not get much information about the father figures among the early Brangwens. Perhaps, these father figures are not strong. Alfred Brangwen does not represent the Law-of-the-Father. So, the son Tom Brangwen is not able to come out of the maternal influence and grasp the sense of patriarchal culture. In the next generation, the oedipal desire is not seen in the sons for their mother. It is indicated in the novel that Fred is the son of the father. Though the elder son, Tom is close to the mother, no abnormality is perceptible in their relationship. Both of the sons have respect for their father. They realize the Law-of-the-Father. Perhaps

they are able to enter the symbolic order, reigned by the Law-of-the-Father. The Electra complex can be traced in the relationship of Tom Brangwen and his stepdaughter Anna. But the attachment to the father does not have a crippling effect on the emotional development of the daughter. She has the sense of her own self. She is able to enter the symbolic order.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out the ecological awareness Gender difference of high school students.
2. To find out the ecological awareness Locality of high school students.
3. To find out the ecological awareness Annual income of parents of high school students.
4. To find out the ecological awareness parents Educational Qualification of high school students.
5. To find out the ecological awareness Type of schools of high school students.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Is there any significance mean score difference between boys and girls in their ecological awareness?
2. Is there any significance mean score difference between rural and urban students in their ecological awareness?
3. Is there any significance mean score difference between parents Educational qualification of students and their ecological awareness?
4. Is there any significance mean score difference between parents annual income of student and their ecological awareness?
5. Is there any significance mean score difference between Government and private school students in their ecological awareness?

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be a significant difference between boys and girls in their ecological awareness.
2. There will be a significant difference between rural and urban students in their ecological awareness.
3. There will be a significant difference between parents Educational qualification of students and their ecological awareness.
4. There will be a significant difference between parents annual income of student and their ecological awareness.
5. There will be a significant difference among Government and private school students in their ecological awareness.

VARIABLES

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Boys/Girls).
- Locality (Rural/Urban).
- Parents Educational Qualification (12th/Degree).
- Parents Annual Income. (Below 60,000/Above 60,000).
- School Type(Government/Private)

Dependent variable are those events which are by hypothesized as dependent on the changes in the dependent variable (Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore District).

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

In the presence study Normative survey method will be adopted. Survey research employee questioner and interview to our people who provide informations about them selfs their attitude and believes demographic (Age,Gender,Income and So on) the survey method can be classified into many,but according to the objectives and hypotheses in this presence study normative survey method will be adopted.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

Coimbatore district is one of the districts in Tamilnadu, India. Coimbatore is finest education district of Tamilnadu. It is the second largest city in Tamilnadu and one of the fastest growing cities in Tamilnadu State. For the present study the investigator select only 6 Schools in and around Coimbatore. Investigator selected Datas will be collected from the samples of 300 students of various Schools.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Sampling procedure is a definite plan determined before any data are actually collected for obtaining a sample from a given population under the simple random sampling technique. This sampling method is used for selecting samples. The study is based on primary data which is collected from 300 school students at higher high level and around Coimbatore district. The sample which was collected from various college located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

Table 1.1
List of schools used for data collection

S. No	Name of the schools	Number of students
1.	GOVT.HR.SEC.SCHOOL, CHINNIYAM PALAYAM	52
2.	GOVT.HR.SEC.SCHOOL, ARASUR	56
3.	GOVT.GIRLS.HR.SEC.SCHOOL, ONDIPUDUR	48
4.	GK K VIDYALAYA HSS , KADUVETTI PALAYAM	44
5.	J C HSS, COIMBATORE	52
6.	ADHARSH VIDHYALAYA MATRICULATION HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL	48

TABLE 1.2
Distribution of samples based on variables

S. No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Gender	Boys	112	37	300
		Girls	188	63	
2.	Locality	Rural	143	47	300
		Urban	157	53	
3.	Par Edu	12th	239	80	300
		Degree	61	20	
4.	Par Inc	Below 60,000	52	17	300
		Above 60,000	248	83	
4.	Schl Type	Government /Aided	156	52	300
		Private	144	48	

RESEARCH TOOL

Tool becomes another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a significant difference between boys and girls in their ecological awareness.

TABLE 1.3

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on gender

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Re-sult
1	Boys	112	1.2516	29	2.022	S
2	Girls	188	1.4212			
Total		300	1.3364	9		

The Table 1.3 shows the mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on gender. The calculate t value is statistically a significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 1 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on gender

Figure 1: Relationship Between Students Gender and Level of Study on Ecological Awareness of High School Students in Coimbatore District

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant difference between rural and urban students in their ecological awareness.

TABLE 1.4

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on locality

S. No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Re-sult
1	Rural	143	1.2812	299	-2.411	S
2	English	157	1.2182			
Total		300	1.2497			

The Table 1.4 shows the mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on

Locality. The calculate t value is statistically a significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 2 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on locality.

Figure 2: Relationship Between Students Locality and Level of Study on Ecological Awareness of High School Students in Coimbatore District

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant difference between parents educational qualification of students and their ecological awareness.

TABLE 1.5

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on Parents educational qualification

S. No	Par Edu	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Re-sult
1	12th	239	1.0691	299	-2.385	NS
2	Degree	61	1.2121			
Total		300	1.1406			

The Table 1.5 shows the mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on Parents educational qualification. The calculate t value is statistically a significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 3 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on Parents educational qualification

Figure 3: Relationship Between Students Parents Education and Level of Study on Ecological Awareness of High School Students in Coimbatore District

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 4:

There will be a significant difference between parents annual income of student and their ecological awareness.

TABLE 1.6

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on parents annual income

S. No	Par Income	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Below 60,000	52	1.3512	299	0.752	NS
2	Above 60,000	248	1.2812			
Total		300	1.3162			

The Table 1.6 shows the mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on parents annual income. The calculate t value is statistically no significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 4 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on parents annual income.

Figure 4: Relationship Between Students school location and Level of Study on Ecological Awareness of High School Students in Coimbatore District

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 5:

There will be a significant difference among Government and private school students in their ecological awareness.

TABLE 1.7

Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on school type

S. No	School Type	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Gov/ Aided	156	1.1812	299	0.712	NS
2	Private	144	1.1102			
Total		300	1.1457			

The Table 1.7 shows the mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on school type. The calculate t value is statistically no significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 5 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in level of level of study on Ecological awareness of high school students in Coimbatore district based on school type.

Figure 5: Relationship Between Students school type and Level of Study on Ecological Awareness of High School Students in Coimbatore District

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- There is significance difference between boys and girls in their ecological awareness.
- There is a significant relationship between medium of study related factors and study of teachers role for higher high students psychological problems.
- There is significance difference between rural and urban students in their ecological awareness.
- There is significance difference between parents Educational qualification of students and their ecological awareness.
- There is no significant difference between parents annual income of student and their ecological awareness.
- There is no significant difference among Government and private school students in their ecological awareness.

SUMMARY

- A study on ecological awareness high school students in Coimbatore district was studied and the findings reveal that there is a significant difference between level of study on ecological awareness high school students in Coimbatore district with respect to gender, locality, parent education, parents annual income and school type.
- A study on ecological awareness high school students in Coimbatore district was studied and the findings reveal that there is no significant difference between level of study on ecological awareness high school students in Coimbatore district was studied with respect to parents income and school type.

LIMITATIONS

- The study has certain limitation, which are as follows:
- Only 300 students are selected as sampling for the study.
- The project has been restricted to analyze and study in study on ecological awareness high school students in Coimbatore district.
- The study is restricted to the school students of Coimbatore

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

- A Similar Study can be conducted for dissertation by taking more number of concepts and students.
- The study can be conducted to other schools around Tamilnadu.
- Present survey helps to investigate the study of teacher role for higher high students psychology.
- A similar study can also be conducted using various variables

The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between gender, locality and parent education on impact of ecological awareness among students .While taking decision on impact of ecological awareness among students their parents income and school type has to be taken for decision making process.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Agrawal, M., Pandey, S., Jain, S., & Maitin, S. (2012). Oral cancer awareness of the general public in Gorakhpur city, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, 13(10), 5195-5199.
2. Altunta, E. , & Turan, S. L. (2018). Awareness of secondary school students about renewable energy sources. *Renewable Energy*, 116, 741-748.
3. Badoni, A. K. (2017). .Comparative study of ecological attitude of rural and urban senior

secondary school students of district Tehri and Pauri of Uttarakhand *International Education and Research Journal*, 3(3).

4. Cil, E. (2015). Integrating botany with chemistry & art to improve elementary school childrens awareness of plants. *The american biology Teacher*, 77(5), 348-355.
5. Harrell, E. (2017). *Ecological Attitude, Knowledge, and Awareness of Teenagers at a Title I High School in Ventura County* (Doctoral dissertation, California State University Channel Islands).
6. Jeelani, S., Sabesan, S., & Subramanian, S. (2015). Community knowledge, awareness and preventive practices regarding dengue fever in PuducherrySouth India. *Public health*, 129(6), 790-796.
7. Kattula, D., Sarkar, R., Ajjampur, S. S. R., Minz, S., Levecke, B., Muliyl, J., & Kang, (2014). Prevalence & risk factors for soil transmitted helminth infection among school children in south India. *The Indian journal of medical research*, 139(1), 76.
8. Mainaki, R., Kastolani, W., & Setiawan, I. (2018). *School Culture and Ecology*. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and ecological Science (Vol. 145, No. 1, p. 012063). IOP Publishing.

APPENDICES

PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA

1. Name of the student :
2. Name of the School :
3. Gender : Male [] Female []
4. Parents Income : Below 60k [] Above 60k []
5. School Type : Government [] Private []
6. Locality : Rural [] Urban []
7. Parents Education : 12th [] Degree []

QUESTIONNAIRE

S.NO.	Question	Answer	
1	Do you take some action to improve the environment in your town?	Yes	No
2	Do you dispose waste in a pond, forest or anywhere around in your home?	Yes	No
3	Do you sort your home waste?	Yes	No
4	Do you think there should be signs for separating big and small waste?	Yes	No
5	Does your town have separate waste containers?	Yes	No
6	Have you ever sent your waste for recycling?	Yes	No
7	Do you think your water consumption is above average?	Yes	No
8	Do you use linen or ecobags when going grocery shopping?	Yes	No
9	Which energy source do you use for heating your home?	Yes	No
10	Do you use products which damage the ozone layer and produce ozone holes?	Yes	No
11	Do you use recycled products?	Yes	No
12	Which means of transportation do use daily?	Yes	No
13	Do you think intentional pollution should be legally punished?	Yes	No
14	Do you assume that local authorities should do something to improve ecological awareness?	Yes	No
15	How much time a month do you spend in nature?	Yes	No
16	Do you think local pollution has already affected your health?	Yes	No
17	Is students would u change locally?	Yes	No
18	Do you find the environment important?	Yes	No
19	Would you like to learn more about ecology?	Yes	No
20	Do you think people care more about the environment after the revolution?	Yes	No
21	Have you heard of any ecology awareness campaigns recently?	Yes	No
22	Do you think there is a link between number tourist and the state of environment in which you visiting?	Yes	No
23	Do you think every visitor should have awareness of ecology pollution?	Yes	No
24	Is students responsible for making sure we have a healthy environment?	Yes	No
25	Is urban people are the worst polluters?	Yes	No